

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH)

Advancing Insect Biodiversity
Monitoring through Automated
Sensors, Deep Learning, and
Citizen Science Data

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AMI	Automated Monitoring of Insects
DSG	Data Study Group
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GradCam	Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping
IUCN	International Union for the Conservation of Nature
LIME	Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
ResNet	Residual Networks
SDM	Species Distribution Models
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
UKCEH	UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology

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1 Executive Summary

The overarching goal in this Alan Turing Institute Data Study Group (DSG) was to advance understanding and support conservation efforts related to insect populations and biodiversity monitoring. This was achieved through the integration of reliable and trustworthy machine learning applications, with datasets provided by the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH).

Our objectives were twofold:

- Develop advanced analytical techniques for generating biodiversity metrics and interactive data visualisations. These tools aim to promote stakeholder engagement and interest in biodiversity monitoring.
- Enhance the transparency of decision-making in machine learning models and increase the trustworthiness of subsequent biodiversity monitoring results.

Our work ultimately contributes to global biodiversity protection by providing tangible, reliable insights and a comprehensive understanding of ecosystem dynamics.

1.1 Challenge Overview

The health of ecosystems is highly dependent on biodiversity and insect populations, which face increasing threats and demand deeper research as conservation efforts intensify. Historically, the diversity of insect species, coupled with their diminutive size and the challenges of effective capture and monitoring, has hindered the creation of comprehensive datasets for informed decision-making in ecosystem preservation. However, recent advances in camera technology, machine learning, and large-scale insect image databases have paved the way for automated monitoring systems.

The UKCEH and its collaborators have been pivotal in these breakthroughs, spearheading the development of the Automated Monitoring of Insects (AMI) systems (detailed in Section 2.1 and [3, 20]). Focused on moth species, the AMI systems have accumulated

substantial insect image data in the field, playing a crucial role in removing biases and providing extensive image repositories that accurately represent insect populations in their natural habitats.

As we increasingly rely on automated sensors and machine learning to monitor species abundance and biodiversity, the interpretability of our models becomes more critical. Understanding why decisions are made, and why misclassifications occur, not only enhances the trustworthiness and transparency of our models but also provides valuable insights for improving model accuracy and reliability. Therefore, our analysis includes a focused effort on model interpretability, aligning with our goal of providing trustworthy and understandable insights into insect populations and ecosystem health.

In the context of this DSG challenge, we used images from both the AMI devices and the Global Biodiversity Index Framework (GBIF) ¹, as well as leveraging existing pre-trained machine learning models to discern trends in species. Our overarching aim was to distill this wealth of information into understandable and engaging metrics that would resonate with both the general public and specialists, fostering a deeper understanding of insect populations and ecosystem dynamics.

1.2 Data Overview

The data provided for this DSG challenge was sourced from three main channels:

- **GBIF Images**

Moth images curated from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) database. GBIF is a globally recognised repository that adheres to strict data standards, ensuring consistent labelling and annotation with common terminology [6].

- **AMI System Images**

Additional insect images were obtained from AMI systems developed by the UKCEH and the Department of Ecoscience at Aarhus University. These autonomous systems ensure robust and

¹<https://www.gbif.org/what-is-gbif>

unbiased image capture. Data for this challenge includes images from AMI sites in the UK and Panama. Species predictions from previous AMI deployments in Denmark and the UK were also used for spatial and temporal analysis of moth populations.

- **Additional Publicly Available Data**

Our analysis also integrated several publicly available datasets to enhance the study:

- **Functional Trait Information:** We used a published dataset covering species traits such as ecology, phenology, conservation status, host plant specificity, breeding habitat, distribution trends, and morphological characteristics [4].
- **Weather Data:** Weather parameters (temperature, precipitation, and sunshine duration) from the Open-Meteo API were incorporated for AMI sampling sites and dates, enabling exploration of species-weather correlations [22].
- **Ecological Raster Data:** Data from Copernicus [11, 12] provided climate information (growing season length, mean daily temperature, precipitation) and land use/cover data from S2GLC 2017 [2]. These datasets offered insights into the ecological preferences and distribution patterns of moth species.

1.3 Main Objectives

The primary objectives of the DSG were as follows:

1. **Generate Comprehensive Biodiversity Engagement Metrics and Data Visualisations**

By using advanced analytical techniques, we aimed to extract comprehensive biodiversity metrics that illuminated intricate patterns within insect populations. Through compelling data visualisations, we attempted to create clear and accessible representations of the biodiversity dynamics, facilitating a nuanced understanding for both experts and non-experts.

2. Develop Model Interpretability Methods

Recognising the importance of transparency and interpretability of machine learning outputs in the context of species classifications in monitoring insect populations, our focus included the design of robust methods for model interpretability. This ensures that the decision-making processes of algorithms are not only accurate, but also comprehensible. By achieving this, stakeholders can trust and understand the insights derived from machine learning models, fostering confidence in the decision-making process for ecosystem preservation and conservation strategies.

1.4 Approach

The technical approaches employed during the DSG event were divided into two streams, as outlined below: (1) Data Visualisation and Biodiversity Engagement Metrics; and (2) Model Interpretability.

Data Visualisation and Engagement Metrics

To understand trends in insect populations and effectively engage stakeholders, various metrics were developed and presented through a comprehensive dashboard. Key approaches are described as follows:

- **Correlation of Species Populations with Weather:** We examined correlations between species populations and daily weather parameters (temperature, precipitation, sunshine duration) using the Open-Meteo API [22], revealing significant associations for specific moth species.
- **Time Series:** The AMI UK dataset was reprocessed to generate daily and hourly time series for different moth taxa, enabling an understanding of seasonal and daily fluctuations in activity.
- **Meaningful Biodiversity Metrics:** Functional ecology metrics were explored, including the classifications of the Red List of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) [17] and biomass, for visualisation. The species richness (the number of

species in a community) and evenness (the abundance of each species, relative to that of other species in a given community) were also calculated to produce a daily time series.

- **Species Distribution Models:** Species Distribution Models (SDMs) were used to identify species' ecological niches or habitats. We used ModEco [7] and Maxent (maximum entropy modelling) [13], two prominent software tools for computing probabilistic models, based on GBIF species observations. We compared GBIF observation locations with the area's environmental variables: daily maximum temperature; growing season duration; and land use. A model was built using the former two as features to determine suitable environmental conditions for a given species.
- **Dashboard:** A comprehensive dashboard was developed using Streamlit [18]. The dashboard included pages highlighting the locations of the AMI systems, family distribution maps, time series of genus and species, weather correlations, species distribution maps, feature maps, and classification interpretability heatmaps.

Model Interpretability

Our approach to interpreting a pre-trained moth classifier involved leveraging the ResNet architecture [9], a deep convolutional neural network designed for image classification tasks, to understand each layer and the reasons why decisions were made. Firstly, we created feature maps to delve into the inner workings of the model. Secondly, we employed Shapley [10], GradCAM [16], and Lime [14] attribution methods to generate heatmaps, highlighting regions of influence within the images, and providing insight into the model's classification reasoning.

1.5 Key Findings and Implications

Our exploration of moth populations and biodiversity metrics through the DSG challenge yielded key insights that have profound implications for ecological monitoring and conservation strategies:

- **Biodiversity Dynamics Unveiled:** Our data visualisations, including time series and correlation analyses, unveiled the

dynamics of biodiversity between various species and their response to environmental factors. It showed that there was variation between species in time series - not all moths come out at the same time.

- **Weather Impact on Moth Populations:** The correlation analysis also revealed significant associations between species populations and the daily weather parameters. Understanding how moths respond to temperature, precipitation, and sunshine duration provides crucial insights for predicting their presence and abundance under changing climate conditions. Notably, these associations were highly species-specific, with certain moth species exhibiting stronger correlations with temperature, precipitation, and sunshine.
- **Identifying Species Niches:** The implementation of Maxent and ModEco played a pivotal role in highlighting specific species distributions and regions of interest. By comparing GBIF observation locations with environmental variables such as daily maximum temperature, growing season duration, and land use, we discerned patterns that define environmental suitability for a given species. These findings are not only instrumental in understanding species-specific habitats but also hold significance for targeted conservation efforts.
- **User-Friendly Dashboard for Stakeholders:** The development of a user-friendly dashboard using Streamlit ensures accessibility for both specialists and non-specialists. This multifaceted exploration not only advanced our ecological understanding, but also establishes a pivotal resource for shaping effective conservation strategies and informed decision-making. By allowing stakeholders to interact with region- and species-specific distribution maps, time series plots, weather correlations, and more, the dashboard empowers users to explore and engage with ecological data in a dynamic and personalised manner.
- **Model Interpretability Enhances Trust:** Leveraging attribution methods like Shapley, GradCAM, and Lime provided transparency into the decision-making process of the pre-trained model. Additionally, the utilisation of feature maps offered valuable insights

into the inner workings of the model by visualising the activation patterns of the network's neurons at different layers. These methods highlighted the key pixels and features involved in reaching a classification decision, enhancing model interpretability and confidence in subsequent insect population records.

These key findings have significant implications for ecological monitoring, conservation efforts, and our understanding of the intricate relationships within insect populations. Application of these insights could contribute to more effective decision-making in the realm of biodiversity conservation and ecosystem management.

1.6 Limitations and Future Work

The exploration of insect populations and biodiversity metrics during the DSG challenge, though fruitful, encountered certain limitations and opportunities for future research.

Data Limitations and Biases

The dataset itself presented inherent problems and biases, warranting acknowledgement:

- **Temporal and Geographical Biases:** The GBIF dataset, spanning from historical museum specimens to recent smartphone photos, introduces temporal and geographical biases as documented in previous studies. While efforts were made to ensure accurate labelling in the dataset curation, changes in species populations over time can introduce biases. Future work should address these issues by incorporating more recent and regionally diverse data from unbiased sources.
- **Imbalanced Species Representation and Taxonomic Biases:** There exist imbalances in the distribution of images among species, influenced by both natural variations in abundance and taxonomic biases in biodiversity data caused by societal preference. These biases impact the generalisation capabilities of related machine learning models.

Time Constraints and Future Directions

The one-week duration of the DSG challenge imposed constraints on the depth and breadth of the analysis, leading to several considerations for future research:

- **Improving Species Distribution in the Image Data:** Future efforts should focus on creating unbiased datasets and augmenting existing ones to ensure a more representative sample of species images. Improving the quality and inclusivity of training data enhances the performance and applicability of machine learning models in biodiversity monitoring.
- **Out-of-distribution Detection for Unseen Species:** The current machine learning models are limited to classifying species present in the training data. However, when encountering new or under-represented species, it is imperative to incorporate out-of-distribution detection methods. These techniques can identify novel species, thereby enhancing the ecological insights provided by the model. Exploring this approach for future research would be particularly valuable, especially in regions with limited documentation of biodiversity.
- **Incorporating Metadata in Species Classification:** Given our findings that various features, such as weather and time, correlate with species abundance, we propose incorporating these features into future machine learning models to provide deeper insights into species likelihood. By integrating additional metadata derived from environmental and temporal factors, we anticipate improvements in model accuracy and classification performance. These metrics could prove valuable in supporting indicators used by environmental decision-makers, including the UK Biodiversity Net Gain metric ².
- **Time Series Analysis Challenges:** Further work could delve into time series analysis to better understand the dynamic relationship between species abundance inferred from the AMI data, seasonal variations, and environmental factors over time. This approach would not only enhance our understanding of ecological processes but also

²<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/biodiversity-metric-calculate-the-biodiversity-net-gain-of-a-project-or-development>

contribute to more effective conservation strategies tailored to the temporal dynamics of ecosystems.

- **Enhanced Deployment and User Training:** The comprehensive dashboard developed during the DSG event has been locally deployed. Post-event work is essential for code refinement and deploying it to a wider audience. Technical enhancements will ensure accessibility and usability for all users. Additionally, prioritising training sessions for users and stakeholders on the dashboard's usage and interpretation will be essential. These sessions will empower users to effectively utilise the dashboard for decision-making and analysis. Actively collecting feedback from users and stakeholders will further enhance engagement and address any usability issues or feature requests.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Recognising the importance of stakeholder engagement, it is important to collaborate with environmental organisations, local communities, and policymakers to refine our metrics and dashboards. This collaboration will provide valuable insights into the specific metrics that resonate most with their objectives and concerns. By aligning ecological monitoring strategies with the needs and perspectives of stakeholders, the scientific rigour of our research can be enriched and its practical impact on environmental conservation efforts enhanced.

Addressing these limitations and pursuing future work in these directions will be instrumental in advancing the effectiveness and robustness of ecological monitoring and biodiversity research.

2 Data Overview

2.1 Dataset Description

The data provided for this challenge is derived from three primary sources:

1. GBIF Images
2. AMI System Images

3. Additional Publicly Available Data Sources

Each of these will be described in detail in the following sections.

GBIF Images

Moth images were obtained from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) database³. GBIF, globally recognised for its contribution to biodiversity data, adheres to strict standards, ensuring consistent labelling and annotation with common terminology [6]. The images within GBIF have undergone rigorous expert verification and labelling processes. Figure 1 showcases examples of the diverse range of images provided by this database.

Figure 1: Example of images included in GBIF catalogue, including high quality smartphone images (left), museum specimen (middle) and different angles (right).

For the purposes of this challenge, up to 1000 images were collected for 428 species known to be found in the UK and Panama, where possible. However, it is important to note that in many cases the availability of images varied, leading to a species bias in the dataset.

AMI System Images

Additional insect images captured by AMI systems, developed by the UKCEH and the Department of Ecoscience at Aarhus University⁴. The AMI device comprises of UV and white lights for attracting and imaging

³<https://www.gbif.org/what-is-gbif>

⁴<https://www.ceh.ac.uk/ukceh-ami-trap-automated-monitoring-insects>

Figure 2: A schematic of AMI system, left, and photograph of the device at the UKCEH, right. This shows a light trap with a light table, a white sheet, and UV light to attract live insects during night hours. The computer vision system consisted of a light ring, a camera with a computer and electronics, and a powered junction box with DC-DC converter.

moths, high-capacity data storage to collate images over long sampling periods, and battery or solar power to allow the system to be deployed away from mains power (schematic in Figure 2). These systems ensure that data were collected autonomously and in a robust manner, thereby minimising bias and improving data quality.

The challenge dataset included images from AMI sites in the UK (Table 1) and Panama. An example image captured from the AMI devices in Farrington, UK is shown in Figure 3.

To conduct spatial and temporal analysis of moth populations, we utilised output classification inferences from previous AMI deployments of a moth species classifier. Data were collected at four locations in the UK between 02/08/2023 and 12/09/2023 (Table 1); one Panama site for 4 nights in January; and for one site in Denmark for 169 nights between 16/06/2022 - 29/11/2022. The number of detections in each region is shown in Table 2. The inferences were provided in CSV files featuring with columns for: path,

Deployment ID	Name	Latitude	Longitude
EO4531A2	East Hendred 1	51.589179	-1.323236
FA4C9783	East Hendred 2	51.583779	-1.334005
O3A2D8FE	East Hendred 3	51.5767289	-1.3458783
13DCA4E9	East Hendred 4	51.5728748	-1.3470788

Table 1: UK Sampling locations, in latitude and longitude, of inferences from four AMI deployments.

object bounding box, area pixels, timestamp, binary label (was the object a moth or non-moth), species (if a moth), score, and sequence frame.

Region/Site	Snapshot Images	Motion Images	Detections
Denmark	26,321	NA	121,492
UK	24,816	261,163	417,613
Panama	293	52,926	

Table 2: Number of inferences provided in dataset for each deployment site.

Additional Publicly Available Data Sources

In addition to the primary datasets sourced from GBIF and the AMI system, our analysis incorporated valuable information from other freely available online platforms, contributing to the holistic approach taken in our study:

- **Functional Trait Information**

In our study, we augmented the analysis by incorporating functional trait information obtained from a published dataset [4]. This dataset includes a wide range of traits such as ecology, phenology, conservation status, host plant specificity, breeding habitat, distribution trend (occupancy), and morphological characteristics. Broader categories, such as those describing habitats, are split into subcategories providing a choice of data resolution.

The conservation status data within this dataset was collated from the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List. Moth species are categorised into nine groups based on criteria such

Figure 3: Example image captured by the AMI system in Farringdon on 22/07/2023. Image shows the device has attracted many species of insects, particularly moths.

as rate of decline, population size, geographic distribution area, and degree of population fragmentation (Table 3).

Overall, the inclusion of this additional dataset enhances the ecological context of our findings and provides a deeper understanding of the conservation implications associated with different moth species.

- **Weather Parameters from Open-Meteo API**

To examine correlations between species populations and weather conditions, we integrated weather parameters such as temperature, precipitation, and duration of sunshine from the OpenMeteo API [22] for the sampling sites and dates. This API serves as a valuable resource for accessing up-to-date and region-specific meteorological data. The incorporation of weather data enriches our analysis by providing insights into the potential impact of environmental factors on insect populations. It enables a more comprehensive exploration of the relationships between species dynamics and climatic conditions.

Abbreviation	Class Name	Description
EX	Extinct	Beyond reasonable doubt that the species is no longer extant.
EW	Extinct in the Wild	Survives only in captivity, cultivation and/or outside the native range, as presumed after exhaustive surveys.
CR	Critically endangered	In a particularly and extremely critical state.
EN	Endangered	Very high risk of extinction in the wild, meets any of the criteria A - E for Endangered.
VU	Vulnerable	Meets one of the 5 criteria on the Red List and is therefore considered at high risk of unnatural (human-caused) extinction without further human intervention.
NT	Near threatened	Close to being endangered in the near future.
CD	Conservation Dependent	A category whose documentation previously was absent.
LC	Least concern	Unlikely to become endangered or extinct in the near future.
DD	Data deficient	
NE	Not evaluated	

Table 3: The International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) conservation status classes.

- **Ecological Raster Data**

For the Species Distribution Models, our study also incorporated ecological information relevant to insect populations. This data was taken from Copernicus raster data [11, 12] which include climate information such as Growing season length, mean of daily mean temperature, and precipitation. Additionally, information on land use and cover was downloaded from S2GLC 2017 [2]. These variables further provide valuable insights into the ecological preferences and distribution patterns of moth species, enriching our understanding of their habitats.

2.2 Data Quality Issues

While the data we worked with provided valuable insights into the biodiversity of moth species, we acknowledge that it is not without imperfections. In the spirit of transparency, we outline some of the known issues below.

Biases in Collective Science

The GBIF database contains an extensive collection of species-occurrence records, providing valuable insights into the distribution and characteristics of various moth species. However, images collected through collective science initiatives may introduce biases, as contributors might focus on well-researched or visually distinctive species, leading to a skewed distribution of images biased toward societally preferred species. While acknowledging these considerations, the GBIF dataset remains a crucial component of this challenge, contributing to the diversity and richness of the data used in model training and evaluation.

Time and Location of Photos

The GBIF dataset spans images from museum specimens collected in the 18th and 19th centuries to smartphone photos recorded in recent days and weeks. However, species populations and expert knowledge may evolve over time, introducing potential biases in the dataset. Similarly, biases are present in through locations and regions studied. Therefore, there is a potential for biases to be present in the data, and some species may be over or underrepresented.

Data Completeness

Additional challenges include entries with missing geographical coordinates and empty sub-directories (genus and/or species) within an insect family. Another challenge is the lack of information on the life stage of some insect species, which is provided in the GBIF metadata. Only 30% of the data is recorded as adult, with most entered as NA. Having complete information on the life stage of each recorded species would

enhance understanding of its movement and associated biodiversity.

Subset of Species Available for Model Analysis

To develop a model interpretability pipeline, we analysed a pre-existing moth species classifier model. This was created using code developed by the MILA group from the Quebec AI institute. The model was trained to identify thousands of species. However, due to storage constraints, the challenge team could only assess a subset of images for 428 species. Therefore a full evaluation of model accuracy was not possible.

3 Main Objectives

The primary objectives of this DSG were structured across two domains: Data Visualisation with Engagement Metrics and Model Interpretability. Each objective contributed distinctively to our overarching goal of advancing understanding and supporting conservation efforts related to insect populations and biodiversity monitoring.

3.1 Data Visualisation with Engagement Metrics

In the realm of Data Visualisation and Engagement Metrics, our objectives centred on delving into the spatial, temporal, and ecological intricacies of insect populations while enhancing the accessibility of our findings. This was achieved through a series of sub-objectives outlined as follows:

- **Spatial Visualisation of Insect Family Habitats:** Employing spatial visualisation techniques to map the habitats of different insect families, our aim was to provide a visual representation of their geographical distribution.
- **Temporal Exploration:** By investigating the temporal aspects of the data, including seasonal and daily fluctuations in insect activity, we aimed to discern species-specific patterns and trends.
- **Incorporation of Weather Variables:** Exploring correlations between weather variables and species distributions, we aimed to

shed light on the impact of weather on insect populations.

- **Species Distribution Models:** Delving into the concept of species distribution models, we aimed to establish ecological niches for various species and to identify suitable ecological environments for them.
- **Biodiversity Metrics Production:** Deriving comprehensive biodiversity metrics based on established threatened species status, our aim was to flag species that require further attention and intervention in the context of conservation.
- **Interactive Dashboard Creation:** The ultimate aim of this domain was to develop an interactive dashboard that visually presents our findings. This dashboard would serve as a user-friendly interface, facilitating accessibility and engagement for both specialists and non-specialists in the field.

3.2 Model Interpretability

Our objective in Model Interpretability was to clarify the decision-making processes of the machine learning model. This supports the DSG goal by ensuring transparency and comprehension in the model's classifications for biodiversity monitoring. By gaining insights into how the model arrives at its predictions, we can identify potential biases, improve model accuracy, and enhance trust in the model's outputs. Ultimately, this contributes to producing dependable biodiversity measures crucial for informed conservation and ecological management efforts. This objective involved three key directions:

- **Model Evaluation:** The moth species classifier model was assessed in the context of a curated subset of images from the DSG datasets. Our aim was to measure the model's species-level performance for that subset, identify strengths, and pinpoint areas for potential improvement.
- **Model Feature Maps:** Delving deeper into the internal mechanisms of the model, we intended to generate feature maps for various network layers. This endeavour aimed to unveil insights into how the model learns and extracts essential features from input images.

- **Generation of Classification Heatmaps:** Using interpretability methods like SHAP, GradCAM, and LIME, our aim was to identify crucial regions of interest within input images. This approach enhances transparency in the model's decision-making, providing valuable insights into influencing factors.

4 Experiments

4.1 Exploratory Data Analysis

Species in our dataset exhibit varying image counts, depending on availability within the GBIF dataset. We attempted to provide up to 1000 images for each species, where available. A histogram was generated to indicate the distribution of image counts per species for those available during the DSG event.

In total, there were images of 428 species available for analysis during the DSG event. Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of image counts per species, highlighting potential biases. This clearly shows two peaks in number of images, around 0 and around 1000 (the target number). This disparity in image counts between species emphasises the imbalanced nature of the dataset, underscoring the need to acknowledge and address this imbalance in subsequent analyses and datasets.

4.2 Data Visualisation and Biodiversity Metrics

To provide a comprehensive understanding of insect populations and their interactions with the environment, our data visualisation and engagement efforts employ various methods. These include spatial distribution mapping, correlation analysis between species populations and weather conditions, time series exploration, and the incorporation of meaningful biodiversity metrics. Furthermore, we presented our findings through an interactive dashboard. Each visualisation method serves a unique purpose, contributing to the overarching goal of understanding biodiversity by displaying patterns within the data. The following sections detail the methods employed, results, and insights gained through each of these visualisation approaches.

Figure 4: Histogram showing the number of images available for each species.

Spatial Distribution of Insect Families

To foster engagement with stakeholders, we created visualisations depicting the distribution of various insect families worldwide. Initially, our GBIF dataset encompassed records from 77 distinct insect families. After filtering out families without images within their genera, or species, and those lacking location data, 58 families remained suitable for analysis. For each of these 58 families, we aggregated records for all species within the family, eliminated duplicates and entries with missing coordinates, and then conducted reverse geo-coding to extract country names from the latitude and longitude coordinates. Subsequently, we aggregated these records at the country level to illustrate the distribution of families globally.

Figure 5 exemplifies the resulting distribution map for the *Sphingidae* family, also known as Hawk Moths. This family of moths are well known for being pollinators and so understanding their distribution is important in the context of biodiversity. In this example we can see the highest number

of observations in India and Australia, with additional observations across every continent.

Figure 5: Distribution of Spingidae family observations in GBIF database at country level.

Understanding the distribution of insect families at a country level provides valuable insights for local stakeholders and policymakers. It enables them to identify the species present within their region, assess potential ecological impacts, and make informed decisions regarding biodiversity conservation, pest management, and land use planning. This information is crucial for prioritising conservation efforts, implementing effective policies, and mitigating the impact of environmental changes on local insect populations.

Correlation of Species Populations with Weather

To assess the influence of meteorological conditions on various species, we conducted an analysis of correlations between species populations

from the AMI data (section 2.1) and daily average temperatures, precipitation levels, and duration of sunshine. The weather data were obtained using the Open-Meteo API for the date and locations (geographical coordinates) present in the AMI UK dataset.

The species exhibiting the strongest correlations with (a) temperature, (b) precipitation, and (c) duration of sunlight were visualised in Figure 6. Our investigation unveiled that temperature and precipitation showed positive correlations with moth populations, whereas the duration of sunlight had a negative impact on their presence. Notably, *Hemaris fuciformis* demonstrated the highest correlation with temperature ($\rho = 0.72$), *Eremobia ochroleuca* with precipitation ($\rho = 0.86$), and *Orthosia miniosa* with sunshine duration ($\rho = -0.54$).

Understanding the relationships between species abundance and meteorological variables is crucial for comprehending ecosystem dynamics and species responses to environmental changes. These correlations provide insights into how weather conditions influence moth populations, aiding in biodiversity conservation efforts, ecosystem management, and climate change adaptation strategies.

Species and Genus Abundance Time Series

To capture the temporal dynamics of moth taxa, time series plots were generated at both daily and hourly resolutions. These plots show the abundance of identified taxa, allowing for a detailed exploration of seasonal and daily fluctuations.

To comprehend the seasonal and daily variations in activity for different moth taxa, the classification output files from the four AMI UK datasets (section 2.1) underwent reprocessing to generate time series of abundance for all taxa identified by the classifier. Time series were calculated at both daily (total abundance) and hourly (mean average abundance across the dataset) resolutions for both genus and species levels. These reprocessed time series facilitated the creation of time series plots for user-selected taxa at daily and hourly resolutions.

Figure 7 illustrates the time series for a specific moth genus, *Acontia*, at sample location 13DCA4E9. This plot showcases the seasonal pattern of observations of this genus (top) and their distribution over the course of a

Figure 6: Correlations of five strongest associations between species abundance and daily (a) temperature; (b) precipitation; and (c) sunshine duration.

day (bottom). In this instance, there is a notable peak on September 22nd, with consistent daily peaks occurring around 10pm and 1am.

Figure 7: Daily (total) and hourly (mean) average observations of *Acontia* in sampling location 13DCA4E9.

Understanding species and genus abundance time series is crucial in the context of biodiversity assessment as it provides insights into the temporal dynamics of moth populations. By tracking fluctuations in abundance over time, researchers can identify trends, detect seasonal patterns, and assess the impacts of environmental factors on moth populations. This information is valuable for biodiversity monitoring, conservation efforts, and ecosystem management.

Meaningful Biodiversity Metrics

To engage both specialist ecologists and non-specialist users, we incorporated meaningful biodiversity metrics into our visualisations. Using functional trait information extracted from a published dataset (discussed in the additional data sources in section 2.1), we visualised the conservation classifications of the IUCN Red List and the observed biomass distribution. Additionally, species richness and evenness (equation 1) were calculated for each species-level time series at a daily resolution.

$$\text{Evenness} = \frac{N(N - 1)}{\sum n(n - 1)} \quad (1)$$

where N = total number of individuals, n = number of individuals for each species.

We generated plots to illustrate the ratio of different IUCN classes observed on each day at various locations. An example of such visualisation is presented in Figure 8, depicting the IUCN Red List classifications for taxa observed on 03/08/2023 at location EO4531A2 (East Hendred). Additionally, from the species counts, we calculated species richness, evenness and total biomass at daily resolution using data from the published dataset. On this date, it was observed that the majority of observed moths were classed as having a least concerning conservation status. Among those with a concerning conservation status, over 75% were classified as vulnerable, with the remainder comprised of endangered and critically endangered species.

Figure 8: IUCN Red List classifications for taxa observed on 03/08/2023 at location EO4531A2 (East Hendred). Abbreviations: VU: vulnerable; CR: critically endangered; EN: endangered; and NE: Not evaluated.

These metrics offer valuable insights into the biodiversity dynamics at different locations and time points, aiding in the assessment of species conservation status, biomass distribution, and community structure. They serve as important tools for guiding conservation efforts, flagging endangered species, and monitoring ecosystem health.

Species Distribution Models

Species Distribution Models (SDMs) are widely used to delineate ecological niches or habitats and analyse their dynamics in response to environmental factors. In this study, we employed Maxent (maximum entropy modeling) and ModEco, software tools for generating probabilistic models based on the spatial occurrences of confirmed species. Computation of the SDMs was performed by utilising species location data (in csv format) and raster data (in asc format) representing environmental variables influencing the spatial distribution of a species' population.

Firstly, environmental variables were overlaid on a map with GBIF occurrence data to visualise how species data correlated with ecological traits. These traits were:

- Mean of the daily maximum temperature near the surface aggregated as an annual average over the months (in degrees Kelvin).
- Duration of the growing season, defined as the number of days between the start and end of the growing season.
- Land use and cover.

Figure 9 illustrates this process for *Adela viridella*, displaying its geographic distribution along with precipitation and land use data.

Figure 9: The location for *Adela viridella* (a) GBIF observations and overlaid with b) precipitation and c) land use over Vienna.

Following this, SDMs were implemented using the Maxent software to explore the association between moth populations and the continuous variables (annual mean of the daily maximum temperature at 2m (degrees in Kelvin) and growing season length). The SDMs predicted the

probability of suitable conditions for a given species based on these environmental variables. The models were visualised on maps, with red indicating high probability of suitable conditions, green indicating typical conditions, and lighter shades of blue indicating low suitability.

A jackknife test was utilised to evaluate the importance of individual variables within the SDM. This method involves systematically excluding each variable from the dataset and recalculating the SDM's performance metrics based on the remaining variables. By aggregating these recalculations, we can determine the relative importance of each variable in predicting the species' habitat suitability. Specifically, a high jackknife of regularised training gain indicates that the variable is a strong predictor of habitat suitability, while a lower value suggests less importance.

Figure 10 illustrates the predicted suitability of conditions for *Adela viridella* centred on Europe. GBIF observations of *Adela viridella* are shown as white dots on this map. Conditions were found to be particularly desirable for the species in southern UK and northern France. Additionally, the Jackknife test indicated the importance of environmental variables in the SDM for this species with air temperature showing the highest regularised training gain value, followed by growing season length.

While this distribution model demonstrated considerable predictive power, through visible association between *Adela viridella* populations (white points) and predicted habitat suitability, inconsistencies were still observed. For instance, the SDM in this case inaccurately predicts habitat unsuitability in certain areas, such as near Vienna (green in Figure 10), despite recorded observations on GBIF (Figure 9 c). Similarly, the model identifies the north coast of the Black Sea as a suitable habitat, however no *Adela viridella* are observed there. Further analysis and additional features are necessary to refine the model's accuracy and to gain a full understanding of environmental conditions.

To enhance the accuracy of the SDMs, we propose the incorporation of additional environmental variables such as monthly or annual precipitation, presence of host plants, soil moisture index, and temperature seasonality.

Figure 10: An example of a species distribution model for *Adela viridella* computed using the Maxent, showing predicted suitability of conditions and Jackknife of regularised training gain.

Dashboard

The creation of a dashboard was a pivotal decision, providing a centralised platform to present and share our findings effectively, especially with stakeholders. We chose to implement Streamlit due its user-friendly interface and documentation, especially compared to other dashboard frameworks such as Gradio [1] and Voila [21]. The dashboard offered an accessible means of interaction and exploration of our results.

Streamlit's smooth integration into Python code eliminated the need for a separate front-end, facilitating rapid prototyping within the project's time constraints. While customisation options were somewhat limited, the simplicity of handling user input with just a single line of code accelerated the development process.

Each component of our project was allocated a dedicated page on the dashboard, serving distinct purposes:

- **Landing Page**
Offered an introduction to the dashboard, featuring a map highlighting the locations of all AMI systems, fostering an immediate understanding of the project's scope and distribution (Figure 11a).
- **Family Distribution Map**
Enabled users to explore the geographical distribution and abundance of selected taxa based on GBIF data, providing insights into the spatial patterns of insect families (Figure 11b).
- **Genus and Species Time Series**
Provided seasonal and daily average time series plots for each genus or species, allowing users to delve into temporal trends and fluctuations in biodiversity metrics (Figure 11c).
- **Weather Correlation**
Illustrated the top correlations between species abundance and selected weather events, shedding light on the influence of meteorological conditions on insect populations (Figure 11d).
- **Species Distribution Maps**
Showcased the predicted habitat distribution of species using Maxent and ModEco software, exemplified by *Adela viridella*, offering insights into habitat suitability and highlighting areas for further investigation and conservation efforts (Figure 11e).
- **Feature Maps**
Visualised the features learned by the species classification model, providing transparency into the model's decision-making process and identifying key factors driving predictions (Figure 11f).
- **Classification Heatmaps**
Allowed users to inspect influential regions in input images (e.g., Figure 12 a) using SHAP, LIME, and GradCAM heatmaps, facilitating interpretability and trust in the model's predictions (Figure 12 b-d respectively). Each interpretation method highlighted slightly different pixels of importance, which emphasised the intricacies and differences between the methods.

Figure 11: Collection of screenshots from the dashboard

- **Future Work**

Outlined recommendations and potential avenues for future research, guiding further exploration and development for the UKCEH and other stakeholders.

4.3 Performance Evaluation

To develop a machine learning model interpretability pipeline, a pre-existing moth species classifier was used, created using code developed by the MILA group from the Quebec AI institute [8]. This ResNet architecture model had been trained on GBIF images for moths found in the UK and Denmark [8]. The model employed the AdamW optimizer, a cosine decay learning rate schedule with linear warm-up, and label smoothing.

To evaluate the model, performance metrics (precision, recall, F1-score and support) for each available species were calculated, as outlined in Figure 13. The support values indicate the number of actual occurrences

Figure 12: Screenshots from the dashboard classification heatmaps page. The raw input image (a) is compared to important features according to SHAP (b), Lime (c) and GradCam (d).

for a class in the dataset. Imbalanced support in the training data may indicate structural weaknesses in the reported scores of the classifier and could indicate the need for stratified sampling or rebalancing. In our data set the support ranges from 1 to 244, indicating that this dataset cannot be used for overall evaluation.

Figure 13: Schematic representation of the model evaluation process.

Table 4 presents the precision, recall, F1-score and support values for three selected classes within the GBIF dataset. These specific classes were chosen to demonstrate the model's performance across different scenarios. We observed that the model generally exhibited high precision across all classes, indicating that when it makes a prediction, it is often correct. However, the recall, or the model's ability to identify all actual instances, varied among classes. Specifically, the model showed high

precision for *Zeuzera pyrina* but struggled to capture many of its actual instances, resulting in lower recall. Conversely, it demonstrated better recall for *Phragmataecia castaneae*, indicating greater proficiency in identifying instances of this class. The F1-score, a holistic metric to capture both precision and recall, revealed a balanced performance in terms of both metrics for *Phragmataecia castaneae*, while opportunities for improvement exist for the other two classes. However, the support values showed an equal number of instances for *Zeuzera pyrina* and *Crosidosema pelebejana*, with fewer instances for *Phragmataecia castaneae*. These support values are crucial for determining whether item sets are sufficiently frequent to be considered interesting or significant.

Classes	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
<i>Zeuzera pyrina</i>	99	65	78	221
<i>Phragmataecia castaneae</i>	92	74	82	93
<i>Crosidosema pelebejana</i>	95	64	76	221

Table 4: Classification report for three selected species.

4.4 Feature Maps

Feature maps are important in the context of biodiversity monitoring and moth species classification because they offer valuable insights into how machine learning models identify and utilise key features (such as edges, textures, or patterns) from the data. Deep Neural Networks, commonly used for image classification tasks like identifying moth species, are often regarded as "black boxes" due to their complex internal mechanisms. This opacity poses challenges in understanding how these models arrive at their predictions, potentially leading to scepticism, potential misuse, and concerns about their reliability.

By shedding light on the visual cues and features influencing model predictions at different layers, feature maps play a pivotal role in enhancing transparency, interpretability, and ultimately, confidence in machine learning models. They provide valuable insights into how these

models process information and arrive at their predictions, empowering informed decision-making in conservation strategies.

In our study, we harnessed feature maps to delve into the ResNet model's intricate architecture, gaining valuable insights into the specific features identified during training. The process, outlined in Algorithm 1, involved selecting an input image, activating neurons in designated convolutional layers, and visualising these in resulting map grids.

Algorithm 1 Feature Map Visualisation. Where *model* is the Pre-trained image classification model, *image* is the input image and *n* is the index corresponding to the convolutional layer of interest.

The data: model, image, n

The result: Display of feature maps for a given convolutional layer, *n*

```
1: procedure VISUALISE FEATURE MAPS(model, image, n)
2:   Load pre-trained ResNet model from model
3:   Extract the nth convolutional layer from the model
4:   Load and pre-process the input
5:   Set the model to evaluation mode
6:   Perform forward pass to get feature maps for the nth convolutional
   layer
7:   Convert feature maps to numpy arrays
8:   Plot and display feature maps
9:   return Displayed feature maps
10: end procedure
```

Figure 14 illustrates a feature map generated for an input image of *Adela cuprella* sourced from GBIF. Each box represents features from across the model's 64 layers, offering a glimpse into how the model learns and prioritises features across layers. The boxes/layers in red highlight where the model learns key features of the moth. Understanding these prioritised features enhances confidence in the model's capabilities and fosters trust in its outcomes.

4.5 Classification Heatmaps

To comprehensively understand and interpret the decisions made by the ResNet model in classifying moth species, we employed three distinct

Figure 14: An image (Adela cuprella, left) input into the ResNet model with feature map extracted (right) to show the features for each of the 64 layers. The layers highlighted in red show features of particular interest in classification.

interpretability methods: SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) [10], GradCAM (Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping) [16], and LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations) [14]. The objective was twofold: to enhance model trust through explainability, and to identify potential avenues for performance improvement. Each method provides unique insights into the model by highlighting areas important in the decision-making processes, thereby enhancing transparency and interpretability.

SHAP, GradCam, and LIME are all methods used for interpretability in machine learning models. In brief, SHAP values provide a way to attribute the output of a model to its input features, offering a ranking of feature importance. GradCam highlights regions of an image which the model is focusing on using gradients, this aids in understanding the model's attention. LIME uses noise to determine which regions of an image are influential. The choice between them depends on the specific interpretability needs and the characteristics of the model and input data.

In applying these methods collectively, our aim was to provide a holistic interpretation of our ResNet model, facilitating a deeper understanding of its decision-making processes. Each method contributes distinct perspectives, collectively enhancing the interpretability and transparency of our machine learning model, while acknowledging their respective advantages and potential limitations.

SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP)

To adapt the SHAP value formula for the specific context of an image classification task, such as identifying different insect species, we must consider its application to a classification model. In this scenario, the model's output represents the probability of an insect belonging to a particular species. Here, each feature i in the SHAP analysis corresponds to a pixel in the image, and the SHAP value $SHAP_i$ signifies the impact of that pixel on the model's prediction for a particular species.

This approach helps identify impactful pixels and, by extension, regions of the image crucial to the model's decision-making process. While it may not directly correspond to specific insect characteristics like wing patterns, shape, or colour, it aids in understanding which visual elements are most significant for the model's classification.

However, calculating SHAP values for a complex model like ResNet is computationally intensive, involving the evaluation of the model's output for every possible combination of input features. This becomes exponentially demanding with an increasing number of features, particularly for high-dimensional data like images.

To overcome these challenges, we integrate GradientSHAP, an efficient alternative within the SHAP framework tailored for complex models. Combining the principles of Integrated Gradients [19] with SHAP, GradientSHAP attributes the prediction of a deep network to its input features based on gradients. Using a gradient-based approach, GradientSHAP approximates SHAP values more efficiently, providing a scalable solution for interpreting models like ResNet.

The implementation of GradientSHAP not only addresses computational challenges but also allows for quick interpretative heatmap generation.

These heatmaps can be integrated into the user-facing dashboard (discussed in the Dashboard section of 4.2), facilitating real-time analysis and enhancing the user experience with immediate and comprehensible results.

Despite being an approximation, GradientSHAP provides meaningful insights. The generated attributions highlight key regions within the input images significantly influencing model predictions. GradientSHAP effectively balances the need for detailed information and computational efficiency. While it may not capture the full intricacy of feature interactions like the exact SHAP method, it offers a practical approach for model interpretation.

Figure 15 presents an example input image of *Adela croesella* (left) alongside its corresponding GradientSHAP heatmap (right), highlighting influential regions for inference and aiding model interpretation. In the heatmap, the colour range represents influence values from 0 (least) to 1 (most).

Figure 15: Comparison between a raw GBIF photograph image (left) and its corresponding GradientSHAP heatmap (right). The heatmap indicates areas of highest influence on the model's classification decision (red, 1) and lower influence (blue, 0).

By demonstrating how the model effectively focuses on key features of the moth itself, such as the antennae, wing tips, and head, while disregarding irrelevant background information, these visualisations enhance our understanding of the model's behaviour. This transparency is essential for ensuring that stakeholders can trust and understand the insights derived from the machine learning model, thereby facilitating informed decision-making in ecosystem preservation and conservation efforts.

Gradient-Weighted Class Activation Map (GradCAM)

GradCAM is a technique that generates visual explanations for model predictions by highlighting the regions in the input image that contribute most to a particular class. This is achieved by examining the gradients of the predicted class concerning the feature maps of a given convolutional layer, typically the last one.

In this challenge, GradCAM was extended to multiple layers of the model to gain insights into how different levels of abstraction contribute to predictions. This involved repeating the process for various intermediate convolutional layers, providing a more nuanced understanding of the hierarchical features that the ResNet model relies on for the classification of moth species. This multilayer approach enhances the interpretability of the model decision-making processes.

In summary, the steps are as follows:

1. **Model Modification:** We adapted the ResNet model to include a hook for the layer of interest, capturing gradients during back-propagation.
2. **Model Forward Pass:** Perform a forward pass through the modified model to obtain the feature maps of the selected convolutional layer.
3. **Calculate Gradients:** Compute the gradients of the predicted class concerning the feature maps, highlighting the importance of each feature map in making the final prediction.
4. **Global Average Pooling:** Aggregate the gradients using global average pooling to obtain a weighted combination representing the importance of each feature map.

5. **Activation Map:** Multiply the weighted combination by the feature maps to generate the class activation map, indicating influential regions in the input image for the predicted class.
6. **Heatmap Generation:** Overlay the class activation maps on the input image to create a heatmap visually depicting important regions contributing to the model's prediction.

GradCAM heatmaps for *Zeuzera pyrina* are shown in Figure 16. Four *Zeuzera pyrina* images were chosen at random⁵. In this example, the three images on the left were correctly predicted by the model, while those on the extreme right were incorrectly predicted as *Yponomeuta evonymella* - a somewhat visually similar white and black-spotted moth. The multipliers, in brackets, quantify the increase in confidence comparative to random chance: $\sim \text{Confidence} / N_{\text{classes}}^{-1}$.

In our analysis, a striking observation arises: the model consistently directs its attention towards the moth itself in the final convolutional layer when making accurate predictions. Conversely, for incorrect predictions, the model's focus shifts towards fragments of the background in the same layer. This insight reinforces the reliability of the model's decision-making, indicating that it bases its correct predictions on relevant subject matter rather than incidental background details. Overall, these findings bolster confidence in the model's outputs for biodiversity monitoring, enhancing its potential utility in ecological research and conservation efforts.

Notably, for incorrect classifications, the model focuses on areas other than the moth. This suggests a potential area for improvement, where future research could explore background removal techniques to assist the model in correctly identifying the moth.

Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME)

LIME is a model-agnostic method that approximates the decision boundary of complex models using interpretable, locally linear models. It achieves this by perturbing input data and observing changes in the model's predictions, creating a local, interpretable surrogate model.

⁵Selected in order of GBIF UUID starting from the smallest

Figure 16: GradCAM heatmaps for four images of moths of the species *Zeuzera pyrina* that have been superimposed onto the original images. This method was repeated after each convolutional layer, and three instances are shown. The multipliers, in brackets, quantify the increase in confidence comparative to random chance. The heatmaps are upsampled and smoothed with Gaussian blurring for visual presentation.

To approximate the local behaviour around the chosen input image, we generated perturbed samples. Small random perturbations in pixel values were introduced to create variations of the original image. Each perturbed image was then fed into the ResNet model, and predictions were recorded. The resulting dataset comprised perturbed samples and their corresponding model predictions, enabling us to discern which pixels were important in specific inferences.

Overall, applying LIME to image classification involved the following steps:

1. **Generating Perturbations:** Perturbed versions of the input image were created by randomly masking or altering pixels while preserving the global structure.
2. **Model Prediction on Perturbations:** Predictions from the ResNet model were obtained for the perturbed images.
3. **Building a Surrogate Model:** A locally linear surrogate model was fitted to the perturbed images and their corresponding model predictions. This simpler model approximated the behaviour of the complex model in the local region around the input image.
4. **LIME Explanations:** The coefficients of the surrogate model were used to interpret the importance of pixels. These coefficients indicated the contribution of each pixel to the model prediction.
5. **Creating Heatmaps:** Heatmaps were generated by highlighting pixels with higher absolute coefficients, representing their significance in the local interpretation of the model's decision.

Table 5 provides the inferences for a given image of an *Adela cuprella* moth. In this example, when inferences were performed using the ResNet model, the model incorrectly predicted it as *Nematopogon adansoniella*, with the correct species ranked third most likely.

Figure 17 demonstrates LIME's application to the *Adela cuprella* image, showcasing regions that positively or negatively impact model predictions. Positive and negative coefficients in LIME represent the influence of specific image regions or features on the final prediction. In the context of a computer vision task, green areas in the output image indicate regions that support the predicted class, while red areas highlight

Species	Probability
<i>Nematopogon adansoniella</i>	0.0211
<i>Nematopogon swammerdamella</i>	0.0199
<i>Adela cuprella</i>	0.0157
<i>Adela violella</i>	0.0110
<i>Tineola bisselliella</i>	0.0083

Table 5: The inferences for an Adela cuprella image using the ResNet model. The model incorrectly predict the species to be Nematopogon adansoniella with the correct species predicted as third most likely.

regions that detract from it. Darker shades signify stronger influences on the prediction. The heatmap in Figure 17 reveals that the model’s attention is not as focused on the moth itself, as it also considers background features. This suggests a potential area for model improvement, emphasising the importance of refining the model’s focus on relevant features.

Through the analysis of coefficients and heatmaps, LIME offers valuable insights into which image regions or features contribute positively or negatively to the model’s decision-making process. These insights can inform model refinement and highlight areas where additional training data or adjustments may be necessary to enhance model accuracy and robustness.

After applying SHAP, GradCAM, and LIME to interpret the decision-making processes of our ResNet model in classifying moth species, we sought a comprehensive evaluation by running the same set of images through all three methods. This was integrated into the interactive dashboard (section 4.2). This comparative analysis aimed to discern the unique insights provided by each interpretability technique and identify potential convergences or divergences in the highlighted regions of interest. By applying these methods collectively and systematically comparing their outcomes on common images, we aimed to gain a more nuanced and robust understanding of the model’s decision factors and enhance the overall interpretability and transparency of model predictions.

Figure 17: LIME heatmap applied to an image of Adela Cuprella. In this instance, the model incorrectly predicted the image to be a Nematopogon adansoniella, while the correct answer was third most likely. The green areas highlight the superpixel regions contributing to each inference.

5 Discussion

This study undertook a comprehensive exploration of advanced methodologies for in-depth analysis of insect population and biodiversity metrics, specifically focusing on the challenges posed by the DSG.

5.1 Data Visualisation and Analysis

In our analysis, we utilised diverse data visualisations, including time series and correlation analyses, to explore the dynamics of biodiversity among various species and their responses to environmental factors. By integrating multiple open data sources, we generated new species-specific biodiversity visualisations, shedding light on the relationships between moth populations and environmental factors.

Recognising the importance of facilitating stakeholder engagement, we developed a dashboard interface to provide accessible tools for interaction and exploration of our findings. This intuitive platform allows stakeholders to engage directly with the data, gaining hands-on experience and exploring areas or species of interest to them. The dashboard's dynamic and personalised features empower stakeholders to

interact with the results effectively, fostering collaboration and facilitating informed decision-making in conservation and ecological management efforts.

5.2 Model Analysis

In our pursuit of moth-species recognition, we adopted a multifaceted approach to dissect the explainability and interpretability of an existing species classifier model. Leveraging techniques such as feature map generation, and heatmap-production methods (SHAP, GradCAM, and LIME), we unravelled the model's learning intricacies. These methodologies provided invaluable guidance to potentially refine pre-processing steps, such as background removal/segmentation, and improving model performance. Specifically, they helped us identify which features the model relies on for classification, understand how these features contribute to its decisions, and pinpoint potential areas for model improvement, such as removing background features.

This not only increases the reliability and accuracy of species recognition but also ensures that stakeholders can trust and understand the insights provided by our machine learning model. Ultimately, this approach enables us to provide more reliable and informative reports on moth populations and thereby support biodiversity monitoring.

6 Future Work and Recommended Research Avenues

As our study delved into advanced methodologies for analysing insect population dynamics and biodiversity metrics, it uncovered valuable insights and highlighted areas ripe for further exploration. In this section, we outline key areas for future work and recommend research avenues that could extend and build upon the findings of our study. From refining model methodologies to exploring new environmental variables and expanding habitat connectivity studies, these recommendations aim to guide future research endeavours towards a deeper understanding of insect biodiversity and ecosystem dynamics.

6.1 Methodological Limitations

While our study employed several methodologies to analyse insect population dynamics, several limitations warrant consideration. Factors such as data availability and quality may have influenced the accuracy and generalisability of our findings. Additionally, the complexity of ecological systems presents challenges in encapsulating all pertinent factors influencing insect populations.

Specifically, one limitation lies in the scope of ecological features incorporated into the SDMs. Furthermore, the availability and quality of data pose significant challenges in ecological modelling. Our study relied on existing datasets, which may have limitations in spatial and temporal resolution, as well as accuracy. Improving data quality and availability through enhanced monitoring efforts and data-sharing initiatives is essential for advancing ecological research and improving the accuracy of predictive models.

6.2 Image segmentation

Our analysis revealed instances where the model extracted features not only from moths of interest but also from their surroundings. Applying a segmentation algorithm as a pre-processing step could enhance the model's accuracy in moth-species recognition by isolating moths from their backgrounds. Therefore, segmentation of moths within collected images is recommended for future fine-tuning and implementation of the models. This also makes the models more generalisable and appropriate for classification of both GBIF and AMI images.

6.3 Identifying Unseen Species

Exploring metadata for species identification and exploring out-of-distribution classifiers to flag species not included in the training set offers promising paths for future exploration. Integration of such supplementary data sources and utilisation of advanced machine learning methodologies could enhance the model's capacity to accurately identify unseen species. This holds particular significance for species lacking training data, a scenario particularly prevalent in less extensively

Figure 18: The workflow to compute the habitat distribution model using Maxent [13] and ModEco [7] with proposed next steps (dashed lines) involving integrating external software and stakeholders for decision making.

studied regions like Costa Rica and Panama, both of which have active AMI deployments.

6.4 Habitat Connectivity

Expanding studies in SDMs and habitat connectivity could further leverage the input data used in this project. However, crucial considerations include selecting additional environmental variables based on the geography of the species, such as soil moisture, seasonal temperature and annual precipitation. Computing connectivity indices, estimating habitat loss during ecosystem transformation, and integrating state-of-the-art software tools such as Graphab [5] and Conefor [15] into the workflow could address these limitations and compute metrics at different scales (global, regional, local, and delta). Figure 18 indicates some such future directions in the SDM workflow using dashed lines.

6.5 Time Series Integration and Analysis

To maximise the value of AMI systems for ecological monitoring, future work should explore the integration of the output data with existing moth time series. This integration would facilitate the understanding of long-term pressures, such as climate change, on moth communities. Analysing the relationships between AMI time series datasets and environmental data could unveil how environmental changes drive shifts in moth communities. Regularisation models could be employed to rank environmental variables impacting different taxa, supporting the modelling of future moth distributions under climate change.

6.6 Enhancing Species Classification with Metadata Integration

Based on our discovery of correlations between species abundance and various environmental factors like weather, habitat conditions, and time, we suggest integrating these factors as additional features into future machine learning models. This integration aims to deepen our understanding of species likelihood by incorporating additional contextual information. By leveraging environmental and temporal metadata, we anticipate enhancements in model accuracy and performance in species classification tasks.

6.7 Engagement with Stakeholders

While direct engagement with stakeholders was beyond the scope of this challenge, the dashboard was designed to facilitate future engagement and understanding. By providing accessible and user-friendly visualisations of insect population dynamics and environmental factors, the dashboard serves as a valuable tool for stakeholders, including policymakers, conservation organisations, and local communities.

The interactive nature of the dashboard allows stakeholders to explore and analyse data relevant to their interests and priorities. For example, policymakers may use the dashboard to assess the impact of environmental policies on insect populations, while conservation

organisations can identify priority areas for habitat conservation and restoration efforts.

We understand that different stakeholders will have different needs. By compiling stakeholder feedback and incorporating additional features based on their needs, the dashboard can evolve into a powerful platform for facilitating dialogue and action on insect biodiversity conservation.

6.8 Implications for Conservation and Management

The findings of our study have significant implications for conservation and management efforts aimed at preserving insect biodiversity. Insects play a crucial role in ecosystem functioning, including pollination, decomposition, and nutrient cycling. Therefore, gaining insights into the factors influencing their populations is paramount for maintaining ecosystem stability and biodiversity conservation. By shedding light on the complex interplay between environmental factors and insect populations, this research could provide essential knowledge to inform conservation strategies and mitigate the potential consequences of climate change on global ecosystems.

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- **The Alan Turing Institute's DSG team**
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⁶<https://www.turing.ac.uk/research/research-projects/amber-ai-assisted-monitoring-biodiversity-using-edge-processing-and>

8 Team Members

Participants

Sonny Burniston is a Machine Learning Research Engineer at NatureMetrics, which specialises in the use of eDNA data for the monitoring of biodiversity. He contributed to this project by developing the code to create the GradientSHAP heatmaps, hosting the heatmaps as a feature on the dashboard, and writing the associated parts of the report.

Matthew Faith is a PhD student at the University of Plymouth, co-funded by DEFRA and the University of Plymouth. His research applies machine learning approaches to marine environmental monitoring data to build an evidence base for policymakers. He contributed to this project by processing the time series and biodiversity metrics, alongside writing and reviewing the report.

Vitalii Kriukov is a postdoctoral researcher at Aston University, working on the pan-European All Data 4 Green Deal project in the fields of data harmonisation, geographic information systems (GIS), spatial analysis and habitat connectivity. He contributed to the challenge by developing species distribution models (SDMs) and writing and reviewing the report.

Rachael Joanne Laidlaw is a PhD student on the UKRI-funded Interactive Artificial Intelligence CDT at the University of Bristol. Her research focusses on transferring machine-learnable knowledge between visually similar animal species from geographically distant ecosystems to efficiently fine-tune classification tools. Rachael acted as challenge cofacilitator and contributed to the project by developing the code to create the GradCAM heatmaps, hosting the heatmaps as a feature on the dashboard, and writing and reviewing the report.

Mahsa Pourhossein Kalashami is a PhD student at the University of Leicester and working on machine-learning-based algorithms for medical data analysis. She is working on analysing magnetic resonance imaging collected from Glenfield Hospital for the diagnosis of cardiovascular-related diseases. Mahsa contributed to the challenge by evaluating the pre-trained model, generating feature maps, and participated in drafting and reviewing the report.

Farzana Rahman is a Lecturer of Data Science at Kingston University in London, UK. Farzana works at the cross-section of computational biology and data science using AI, Large Language Models (LLMs), and deep learning. Farzana contributed to the challenge by working on the Exploratory data analysis (EDA), evaluating pre-trained model, working on dashboarding as well as writing and reviewing the report.

Arpita Saggur is a PhD student at the UKRI CDT in AI for Medical Diagnosis and Care at the University of Leeds. Her research focuses on simulation of virtual patients to support medical training. She contributed to the analysis of weather correlations and the spatial distribution of data, and incorporated these into the dashboard and writing and reviewing the report.

Asger Svenning is a PhD student at the Department of Ecoscience — Applied Biology — at Aarhus University, working broadly on scalable biodiversity monitoring with a focus on computer vision and insects. Asger played a role in processing the pre-trained model, assessing its performance, producing GradCam classification heatmaps, and making contributions to the challenge report.

Cameron Trotter is a postdoctoral researcher at the British Antarctic Survey and works on automating the detection and classification of taxa found in benthic imagery. He acted as a co-facilitator during this challenge and contributed to the project by developing and deploying the Streamlit dashboard as well as writing and reviewing the report.

Kaiwen Zuo is a first-year PhD student at the University of Warwick. His research focuses on LLMs and Graph neural networks (GNNs).

Principal Investigator

Katriona Goldmann is a research data scientist at the Alan Turing Institute and works on the AMBER project in collaboration with the UKCEH. As PI, she helped scope the challenge, define the research questions, and prepare the relevant data. She also developed some of the LIME pipelines during the event and led the report drafting process.

Challenge Owner

David Roy is an ecologist whose research focuses on biodiversity monitoring through a combination of citizen science approaches and new technology. He leads projects across the world to develop and test Automated Monitoring of Insects (AMI) systems, aiming to engage people in the amazing world of insects and to provide much-needed data to understand biodiversity trends. David offered crucial technical insights to support the Challenge team, providing a comprehensive understanding of the business problem, the dataset, and the previous approaches tried.

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